

**GLOBAL CHALLENGES IN TEACHING AND LEARNING OF
LITERATURE AND CULTURE**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8324699>

ABSTRACT

The aim of this essay is global challenges in teaching and learning of Literature and Culture. The paper examine how teachers can teach and enhance learning by incorporating topics inside the syllabus about happenings in the world and their direct environment to make their lessons in Literature and Culture interesting and knowledgeable to their students. The method is qualitative and the theoretical framework of the study is Emile Durkheim 1956 Social Functional perspective theory that postulates that society can evolve over time and that if a new need arises, then a new system or structure can be formed to meet that need. And, so, is literature and culture, they are dynamic. The objective of the paper is to enhance the teaching and learning of literature and culture to students. The study found out that the world keep changing in all ramifications and teachers have to move with the times. The study recommends and concludes that a global teacher is a dynamic person that will be ready to embrace all positive ideas to make his/her class apt and modern.

Keywords: Culture, Global challenges, Literature, Teaching and Learning.

*“The stick that comes out of the river does not capsize the canoe”
-Ndokwa proverb*

Introduction

This paper is an exposition on the global challenges of teaching Literature and Culture. Often in the past, the saying “the world is a global village” seemed farfetched and futuristic but not anymore. The world has truly become a global village especially with the launch of the internet and all its many technological benefits. Most activities in the world no matter how remote, dense or local can be uploaded and transmitted to every smart device in a matter of seconds. Challenges are call to justification of something, a provocation to dare and conquer. Challenges are divinely designed to put us on our guide to think, and act appropriately in any situation that does not suit us and our environment. When challenges occur, man must seek for solutions. It is as a result of man’s many challenges that brought about numerous outstanding innovations that we have today. So, challenges are good, for without them a society may remain static.

Objectives of the study:

- To help teachers improve their teaching of literature and culture.
- To enable them recommend good texts for study in class.
- To encourage teachers to go for training and retraining for better knowledge delivery.
- To help teachers incorporate new field of study to their syllabus.

Literature review

There are many benefits in teaching and learning of culture and literature in modern day world. First the teacher has to prepare him/herself well to meet up with the right tool to accomplish his /her objectives. Aside getting a good education and qualification to teach the subject they have to go for training and retraining to be expert and to be on top of their game. Literature not only entertain, it enlightens, educate and sharpen our intellects as individuals and other things, that will improve

the individual knowledge of the others culture, traditions, customs, world view, environment, taboos and acceptable norms. In teaching and learning literature and culture, a teacher has to incorporate world happenings into his teaching. There are many resources available on the net to make the teaching and learning of literature and culture very interesting. What is good for one culture is a taboo for another culture. "Literature are bodies of work that comprises of poem, drama, prose, technical papers, newspapers, magazines, textbooks in all subjects and so on for education, entertainment and for pleasure" Odewumi (2007, p. 2). According to La Morte (2016) culture are all ways of life including arts, beliefs and institutions of a population that are passed down from generation to a generation. Culture has been called a way of life for an entire society. Study.cum agreed with La Morte "culture unites people of a single society together... beliefs, traditions" and Scott, (2014) opined, culture is all that is in human society which is socially rather than biologically transmitted. Meaning you don't have to be biologically related to be in a culture. Culture is also a priceless elements of human existence that can't be assigned a monetary value or explained with a cold logic. It is a shared language, value, norms, traditions, pastimes, customs, beliefs and conventions that cause people to identify with one another John shady (2016). So, in teaching culture and literature one must encompass everything that will make it not only interesting but enlightening.

What is global challenges?

Global challenges are phenomenon world ordeal that is experienced by almost everyone directly or indirectly. It ranges from natural to human disaster that affect education, agriculture, science, health, economy, culture, religion and daily living. According to Díaz-Pérez, F.J, Diez-Bedmar, M.B., Garcia-Ramiez, P., Rasio Moreno, D. (2013), global issues are problems affecting the world or issues of global concern. Gelsdorf (2010) describes it as a major trend, shock and development that has the potential for serious global impacts, such as climate change, extreme poverty, inequality, financial, food crisis, water scarcity, energy scarcity, population growth, demographic shift,

energy security, migration

population, growth, demographic shift, Urbanization, health pandemic and infectious disease.

Our focus here is education and how to teach literature and culture. So, the global challenges in this two areas are: severe lack of trained teachers, especially female teachers. Lack of basic literacy, [A Publication of College of Languages and Communication Arts Education, Lagos State University of Education](#)

numeracy and digital skills to compete for jobs in the future. Lack of funding for education. Gender parity. Government genuine response. Teachers training and development scale. Everyone's involvement (both government and non-government). Confirm appropriate roles for technology. Terrorist. Commodity component (availability of books and how to sort them through different donor platforms like USAID – hosted book alliance). Annual high-level stock take at the G-7 as is done in the US, let us have our own stock taking team. Asides these, the major issues and challenges facing education are: Govern insufficient fund, nment funding; safety. Disciplinary policies: not equal for all student. Technology in education: help active learning, fast access of facts and visual facts and learning. Charter schools and voucher programs, (combination of private and public sponsorships that does not take everyone) – this allows parents to use public funds to send their wards to any school of their choice. Common core – what standards of academic choice a student can learn in mathematics and language arts testing – an objective testing for all. Teacher's salaries - teachers must get the same salaries across the board. The teaching of evolution - teachers should not dwell on evolution because of its multifaceted depth that can lead to religious arguments that can cause problems.

Teacher's tenure should be objective, replace only when necessary. Bullying – bullying should be discouraged and appropriate punishment meted to the bullies and good counsel to the survivor. Class size – there should be a specific class size that will make teaching and learning conducive. Poverty- affects both teacher and student. Learning outcomes, poor students might not be able to afford books or borrow from peers. According to Trade-schools (2021), teachers have to do more and sometimes take the blame for their failures. Other sources mentioned: safety and security for all, quality of teaching, supply of top quality food, payment of bills and getting fees, misbehaviour, retraining and improvement of reputation, maintenance of overall quality, maintenance of hostels quality and first aids or dispensary, solution to many problems, management of laboratories, conducting examination professionally, materials management, improving confidence and maintenance of infrastructure. If we want to mention or list the global challenges, it will never end, as the Igbo will say *chi-ge-eji, chi-ga- abo*. So, the major teaching and learning outcomes is for us as teachers to teach, while the students listen in a face-to-face class, but with technology we can have synchronous and asynchronous as well. (Ulema Conference, 2018)

Who is a global teacher?

A global teacher is one with a mind-set that translate personal global competence into professional classroom practice. The teacher must have a vision of equitable teaching and learning goals that enables students to succeed in an ever-changing world. Also, a global teacher is one who is able to work in a multi-cultural context in this extremely globalised world. They will be able to teach their students about various themes, for instance : sustain able development,

interdependence, cultural identity and diversity, equality, social justice and migration, <https://www.screbd.wm>> document.

Characteristics of a global literature teacher

She/he must create a classroom environment that values diversity. Integrate global learning experience into the curriculum and facilitate intercultural innovation and partnership.

Qualities of a global literature teacher

You must rethink the role of English. Reconsider your role as a teacher, Change your classroom atmosphere, integrate global realistic topics into your teaching, experiment with global education activities and make use of your international experience in your class.

What should be a global literature teacher priority?

As teacher of literature in English, there is the need to lay emphasis on global education goals as self-awareness of their personal identity, culture, beliefs, and how these connect with a wider world, social awareness including empathy, prospective thinking, appreciating diversity, respecting others, relationship building with diverse individuals and groups. Cates (1990) avers “interest in global Education is connected with the rethinking of goals, the “why of teaching English literature content, the what of education. He explains the former by saying that educators teach English because it has always been on syllabus but that, as a consequence of being busy with teaching of grammar, communication, literature, and the daily routine of classrooms. They find it easy to forget “what It’s all for?” he illustrates this idea with the following joke about English acronyms: “Of all the different types of English teaching, TEFL (Teaching English as a Foreign Language), TESL (Teaching English as a Second Language), TESOL (Teaching English to speakers of the other Languages) and so on. The most common type of English taught in classrooms round the world is TENOR (Teaching English for no Obvious Reason).” (Cates, 1997, p. 39). But we are going to learn how to teach English today for obvious reasons; examine the challenges, proffer solutions and recommendations.

What is literature?

A body of works that educate, enlighten, entertain and exposes the world in print, through poetry, play and prose, Odewumi, (2007). Literature can also be define as written works, especially those considered of superior or lasting artistic merit (The Oxford Online Dictionaries, n.d.).

How do you teach literature?

The following methods are helpful in teaching and learning of Literature according to <https://www.indeed.com>> how-to –teach –literature: develop critical thinking skills, offer cultural knowledge, provide vocabulary in context, enhance writing capabilities. Start with short stories,

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then focus on the elements of the story. Involve reading methods, use engaging texts, show age-relevant media, visualise concepts, meet with your students one-on-one, assign small group discussions, assign creative projects and if you can, host a writer's workshop. All of this will make your students well prepared to participate and join world class students and defeat all challenges.

Challenges facing teaching and learning of Literature.

Low Language proficiency level, lack of; reading skills, low motivation, self confidence, prior knowledge of Literature, student's awareness of the importance of learning literature and different preference for other subjects of study and cultural prejudice when, assigned to the category. Besides all of the above weakness in the language, makes the learners concentration more on other aspect of study and other disciplines. We also have the problem of lack of appreciation on the genre that a teacher is teaching. A teacher may be teaching proverbs, yet a learner does not see the sense of passing knowledge through such means. <https://essaykitchen.net>>english>teaching

Solutions:

As a teacher, please prepare your lesson well, change your approach and methodology, use simple vocabularies, select interesting texts, start from simple everyday experience, before delving into difficult foreign text written in colloquial English. You can recommend abridge version of foreign text for essay understanding. Leave language issues to language teachers. Let them understand the basics, they should be able to enjoy every class. Understand your student needs by providing some of the texts for them from your repository of books. Make your class exciting with your personality and knowledge. Study widely your nation's literature and be able to juxtapose it with other cultural societies of the world; especially indigenous language system, example of proverbs equivalent in other cultures and society of the world. Introduce humour: e.g., "Rolling stone gathers no moose" as compared to its Pidgin English version "Rolling stone, na person push am".

What is culture?

The Oxford Online Dictionaries (n.d.) defines culture as the arts and other manifestations of human intellectual achievement regarded collectively or the ideas, customs and social behaviour of a particular people or society. Culture is the lifeblood of a vibrant society expressed in the many ways we tell our stories, celebrate, remember the past, entertain ourselves and imagine the future. According to <https://simplicable.com>>culture>. Culture is also shared language, values norms, tradition, pass time, customs, belief, convention, that cause people to identify with one another. Culture is the lifeblood of a vibrant society expressed in the many ways we tell our stories expression helps define, who we are, and helps us see the world through the eyes of others. In essence, culture is a unique way of life of a particular people in any given society.

What are the global challenges of teaching and learning culture?

You must understand and identify the different learning challenges amongst your students as opined by Chouari (2016):

Students' family problems like religion and customs, lack of funding, ethnicity, racism, inequality, different epistemologies i.e., the theory of knowledge, especially as regards its methods, validity, and scope, the distinction between justified belief and opinion.

How does Globalization affect culture?

Globalization of culture contributes to the exchange of cultural values of different countries. It helps converge their traditions, it helps converge businesses and consume culture between different countries of the world, and it helps the growth of international communication. Aside this globalisation, has affected Africans negatively by loss of one's cultural identity and even national identity <https://mmedwinpublishers.com.PhlJ>

The challenges of teaching culture

A teacher might struggle to teach in absence of a common lingua franca or language in classroom as the case is in Nigeria, and how to unite the various cultural groups. <https://library.lated.org/view,> others are

Figure out how thorough the student are comprehending the material or lesson. Tension between people with different cultural background. Some will have a hard time to integrate into a particular society, the language barrier is a big problem especially in multiculturalism society like Nigeria, the local population may be sceptical toward the new concept, fear of losing their identity in multiculturalism. Tribalism, nepotism, language, stereotypes and prejudice, signs and symbols. Belief and behaviour e.g., "us versus them" and ethnocentrism.

Solutions: Embrace diversity, encourage open communication, lead open discussion team on norms and share company. Modify the syllabus to reflect it multicultural and multilingual/culture society. Accept the unique way that minority families involve in their children's education. Consider the cultural and linguistic challenges families face when communicating with you and the school. Communicate with families to find the optimal ways to communicate with them.

Learn about your student's families. Cultural assumptions about communication with teachers, staff and the school. Encourage Language shock activities i.e., understand what it feels like learning a new Language and culture. Have a high level of tolerance towards the minority class, this will lead to a more peaceful co-existence in the society, because we become more knowledgeable about different culture. Be tolerant, encourage multiculturalism, it makes life more interesting and enhance connection with different people of the world. This is an important part of modern tolerant society. Do not prejudice, treat everyone equally. Avoid ethnic pluralism, especially in a multicultural society. Multiculturalism provides us with a variety of different foods, clothes and activities. Avail yourself the opportunity to learn a new Language

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because, it help improve confidence levels in minorities. Multiculturalism can also benefit companies. It can foster technological progress, it can also improve the general aura and chances in the lives of many people. All of this will help teachers achieve the seven major material culture factors according to <https://www.birdvilleschools.net>>materialnamely: social organization, Language, customs and traditions, religion, arts and literature, forms of government and economic systems. All these align with the global challenges facing the teaching and learning of Literature and culture.

birdvilleschools.net>materialnamely: social organization, Language, customs and traditions, religion, arts and literature, forms of government and economic systems. All these align with the global challenges facing the teaching and learning of Literature and culture.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby made that the English Language teacher must:

- Carry out research frequently and attend conference of English Teachers Association (ELT)
- Operate an open-door policy with the students and community.
- Be guided
- Not be over-zealous or over excited
- Be open to new ideas and technology.
- Attend training and retrain.
- Love him/herself and what you do.
- Inculcate tech teaching methods through zoom, telegram and WhatsApp
- Both institution and teachers should go for human capacity development training.
- Increase staff welfare scheme
- Include entrepreneurship education in your topic, also as a teacher you need this skill too
- Not be a conservative teacher, please do blending.
- Let's practice thinking, not rushing.
- De - lecture the lecture by being all inclusive.
- Let your content be issue-based.
- Let's abolish curriculum apartheid. Let's include everything important when we teach literature and culture.

Conclusion

Every teacher wants ultimate success of his/her pupils no matter which part of the world they reside. So literature text must be properly and rightly recommended and culture of other pupils in the class should be learnt carefully and incorporated into the syllabus. Teachers must be sensitive and not to be prejudice to other pupils' culture. According to (OECD and Asia society 2018,p. 12) in Reimers (2020), there four key aspects of global competence for global youth cited extensively i) investigate the world beyond their immediate environment by examining issues of global and cultural significance. ii) Recognise, understands, and appreciate the perspectives and world view

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of others. iii). Communicate ideas effectively with diverse audiences by engaging in open, appropriate and effective interactions across culture and iv). Take action for collective well-being and sustainable development both locally and globally in any part of the world, be it environmental disaster, terrorism, or shift in literature and culture. Teachers must be aware, because the world is now a global village, an event within minutes can be viewed by people all over the world, if they are connected to the internet or have a good android phone. So all teachers must be well equipped so that they can teach effectively. Challenges will surely come, no doubt, but with it comes solutions as asserted by Achebe (2006) who says as men has learnt to shoot without missing, Eneke the birds have learnt to fly without perching. So teachers should learn to stretch themselves and their lectures beyond the classroom.

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